

Digital Transformation' Effect on Infodemic

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ABSTRACT

With the growing stream of continuous information updates, selecting suitable news is becoming increasingly complicated. Does reduced scrutiny of news make it harder to identify misinformation? And has the population of the Netherlands already encountered fake news? Through literary research and a survey study, this paper examines the impact of digital transformation on the infodemic. This study suggests that forced digital transformation is an accelerator for the degree of infodemic.

Keywords infodemic, digital transformation, misinformation, disinformation, fake news, media

INTRODUCTION

In 2018 a video of Obama was released with the title: 'You won't believe what Obama says. This video turned out to be a deepfake of Obama, created by Jordan Peele to increase awareness about fake news (Rivera, 2018). With the ongoing digital transformation new ways to spread misinformation increase rapidly. This paper aims to create profound knowledge about digital transformation's effect on the infodemic. Infodemic refers to the tremendous amount of information available, including false or misleading information. An example of too much information is the most used social media platform Twitter, in which 6,000 tweets per second are published (Ruby, 2022). This exemplifies the tremendous amount of information, whereby this amount of published information is distributed by just one social media platform. This paper will first describe the problem statement, followed by the research question. Then the literary background information is elaborated, after which the methodology of research and analysis is described. Following that, the results are presented, whereupon the analysis and assessment of these results can be found in the discussion, ending this paper with a conclusion.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

As Jordan Peele showed with the deepfake video of Obama, the emergence of AI our society no longer can assume all online information is valid. Before the internet, publishers had control over what information was published (Althaus & Tewksbury, 2000) in newspapers, on the radio, or in the evening news. Nowadays, as a result of the digital transformation driven by businesses, any individual can publish unverified information. There has been a lot of research into the effects of misinformation. One study concluded that misinformation and fake

news adversely impact supply chain resilience (Chatterjee et al., 2022). Another study referred to several hazardous situations which arose during the pandemic, as a result of the spread of misinformation, in which one example was the observation of several deaths from a chloroquine overdose due to news this was a drug to treat Covid-19 (Tasnim et al., 2020). However, no research is found about the effect of digital transformation on the infodemic.

This research is relevant for academia because of its exploratory research characteristic since there is no preceding research into the effect of digital transformation on the infodemic. For businesses, more information about this effect can result in a better understanding of the issue. In the field of information management, the impact of the infodemic is a relevant topic because the way our society and businesses interact with information changes constantly.

RESEARCH QUESTION

The following research question is formulated:

'How did the digital transformation of the media affect the infodemic?'

The following sub-questions are formulated:

Theoretical questions:

1. What is an infodemic?
2. What is fake news / misinformation / disinformation?
3. What is media?
4. What is digital transformation?

Practical questions:

5. How did digital transformation affect the media?
6. What effect does media have on an infodemic?
7. What effect did an infodemic have on media channels?

THEORY

Infodemic

In this paper, we define the term infodemic as an epidemic of information resulting from many interacting and overlapping processes. These processes are the production, consumption, and amplification of information online (Briand, et al., 2021). The most recent and clear example of an infodemic is during Covid-pandemic, which is still

an ongoing topic. Since the first infections in Wuhan, everyone was curious to know about Covid. News channels started sharing the latest facts and general information about the topic, and people all over the world started sharing their beliefs and thoughts. This automatically results in a bigger information stream from the media across all platforms. All those information streams together form an infodemic.

Fake News

Fake news is verifiably false reports of events deliberately written to mislead readers. Also, content news that aesthetically resembles mainstream news that is extremely inaccurate (Petratos, 2021). Actions and behaviour that are related to the term fake news are: disinformation, manipulation, falseness, rumours, and conspiracy theories. These terms have existed as long as humans were able to communicate. Since digital transformation and thus new communication technologies, new ways of producing, distributing, and consuming news have begun to take place. Due to digital transformation, it is more difficult to differentiate what news to trust. Fake news is also associated to propaganda, in this case, news is created by a political entity (Kalsnes, 2018).

Misinformation & Disinformation

Misinformation and disinformation are often confused with each other. Misinformation can be defined as wrong information or inaccuracies that are accidental without manipulative or malicious intentions (Petratos, 2021). However, the intentions of misinformation are difficult to ascertain whether the falsehoods are deliberate. For example, it is difficult to measure if an accidental falsehood was indeed accidental. Disinformation is defined as deliberately influencing the opinion of those who receive information (Petratos, 2021). Because disinformation has deliberated intentions it can be linked to fake news.

Media

The media can be defined as the total of all media that creates content for the needs of specific audiences both online and offline (Tomyuk & Avdeeva, 2022). In this research, we define the various media channels as: newspapers, news sites, social media, radio, and TV shows. These types of media are also used in the survey that is distributed for this research. Media can be divided into traditional media and new media. In which traditional media is allocated in newspapers, television, and radio. New media is allocated to all information distributed online, for example, on social media such as Twitter and websites (Rajendran & Thesinghraj, 2014). The media plays a major role in the distribution of fake news, misinformation, and disinformation which can result in an infodemic. Media freedom plays an

important role in determining how reliable news is. This is one example to determine if news contains fake news, misinformation, or disinformation (Ryabinska, 2011).

Digital Transformation

Digital transformation can be seen as existing analogue businesses and processes (or manual operations in businesses) that are being replaced by digital computer structures (Burmeister, Luetgens, & Piller, 2016). This results in fundamental changes and impact within organizational strategy, structure, and the distribution of power (Teichert, 2019).

CONCEPTUAL MODEL

Figure 1. Conceptual model

This research aims to understand how digital transformation influences the infodemic and how this correlates with the transformation and the role of media.

Hypotheses

The three hypotheses below are formulated to form a better grip on understanding the correlation between the media and the infodemic.

H1: The media has an enhanced effect on infodemic.

H2: Digital transformation amplifies the effect of infodemic.

H3: Digital transformation has increased the amount of fake news.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

To conduct this research a combination of primary and secondary data is used. Primary data is used through a survey to obtain quantitative data and insight into how citizens in the Netherlands are affected by digital transformation in relation to the infodemic. Secondary data is used to provide knowledge for this research. Besides creating knowledge, it will be a foundation for the statements made in this research.

Primary Data

The self-constructed survey (see Appendix 1. Survey) is digitally distributed via Google forms. The population of the study is Dutch citizens. The chosen sampling frame are Dutch residents within the researchers' professional network, and thus, convenience sampling was chosen because it is inexpensive and fast. The inherent risk is lower

generalisability, where education level and age are not expected to be representative of the population. Nevertheless, this risk is accepted as a trade-off for respondents due to the relatively short research time. To improve the response rate, trust has been sought to be maximized by ensuring anonymity and naming the organization for which the research was conducted (Tilburg University). A total of approximately 300 individual connections were reached, of which 80 responded, which gives a response rate of 26,67%, which is higher than expected for external surveys (10-15%) (BRT lecturers, 2022). Google forms has been chosen because of the ease of use, the accessibility, and the option to gather and store the responses anonymously and safely. The survey will clarify how respondents experience the credibility of the various media. How likely it is that they encountered fake news in the media? And to what extent do the respondents associate the various media with fake news? For the survey, the researchers formulated three general questions for age, gender, and education level (see Appendix 2. Graphs). One question is to determine which media channels are used. Two questions are whether they encountered fake news and when they first encountered fake news. And sixteen questions were based on a non-comparative scale, more specifically the Likert scale, with the option to scale from one to five. The results will be analysed by adding all the responses into graphs and diagrams and stratifying the results. After this, the quantitative data can be compared and analysed and used to measure the perception of citizens in the Netherlands on digital transformation.

Secondary Data

To clarify the definitions of infodemic, misinformation, disinformation, fake news, and media, secondary data is used. This is done by literature research from peer-reviewed journal articles and conference papers, considering their scientific impact and ranking. To ensure the validity of the literature, the researchers used search engines from Tilburg University, Google Scholar, ScienceDirect, and World CAT.

Data Analysis

Combining the primary and secondary data, will provide an answer to the research question: '*How did the digital transformation of the media affect the infodemic?*'. Four theoretical questions are formulated and three practical questions to support the research question. The theoretical questions are answered with the use of secondary data (literature research). The practical questions are answered by a combination of primary (survey) and secondary data. Combining the theoretical and practical sub-questions an answer to the research question will be given in the results.

RESULTS

Digital Transformation of the Media

In 1992, the *Chicago Tribune* became the first media company to publish its newspaper online. In the coming years, other major newspapers followed, including the New York Times and the Washington Post (Salaverría, 2019). The proliferation of digital media was so rapid that, almost immediately, those publications became known as the fourth medium (Bonnington, 1995), in competition with the press, radio, and television. In 1996 several countries had media companies that transformed their analogue media to digital media using the World Wide Web, these media companies were almost always driven by newspapers (Salaverría, 2019).

After the increasing popularity of the Word Wide Web, the first signs of a phenomenon appeared: the active participation of citizens in public communication, which transformed the role of the traditional media even more. (Salaverría, 2019). The appearance of blogs signalled the start of this phenomenon, which rapidly incorporated the voice of citizens into public communication in general (Orihuela, 2004).

As an effect of this change, digital media companies such as *OhmyNews* were introduced. *OhmyNews* was in 2000 one of the first digital platforms that had the option for citizens to publish their own news articles. However, this turned out to not be successful and *OhmyNews* changed its business to a platform about citizen journalism (Gillmor, 2004).

The option for citizens to produce their own news caused an irreversible transformation in the relationship between media and the public. Citizens were no longer on the receiving end of media but they could participate, this was labelled as collaborative journalism (Bruns, 2005).

This led to the creation of social media platforms such as Facebook and Twitter. These digital platforms gave citizens participating power to create their own stories and publish them on the world wide web. These platforms became popular due to the introduction of smartphones which made these platforms very accessible (Mitchell et al., 2012).

Another factor that made these digital platforms so popular is the ability to ignore geographic limits. Digital media was accessible by someone who had a connection to the internet. There were no longer physical obstacles (Salaverría, 2019).

The digital transformation of the media is led by the introduction of the World Wide Web, it gave citizens participating power in the media. This has caused an abundant growth of information.

However, the quality of the information must be questioned more than ever before (Kim et al., 2014). All users on social media platforms are able to write a post and share their beliefs and opinions.

This has caused an increase in misinformation and disinformation. Before the internet misinformation and disinformation already existed but this information was never as accessible as it is today. No physical boundaries limit the option for citizens to receive whatever information they like (Sunstein & Vermeule, 2009). The digital transformation of the media has led to more citizen participation in the media, this has increased the amount of information, especially misinformation and disinformation.

Effect Media on Infodemic

Nowadays, it is possible to spread rapidly information to a larger audience, due to easy access of technology. A good example is social media. This exists of different platforms to widespread information (Raj & Meel, 2022). The amount of users for each platform is visible in Appendix 2 – social media platform.

Different media literacies can help reduce misinformation and infodemics. Furthermore, people have different information sources to consume news. Despite the fact that social media supports the dissemination of information, it also helps in the democratization of information. Traditional media sources, with credible and verified information, also have a chance to reach people through social media to contradict the dissemination (Su, Lee, & Xiao, 2022).

A popular argument is that an abundance of news or information is a given problem for people to locate trusted resources and reliable guidance. Based on literature this is more nuanced and speaks of simplistic fears (Simon & Camargo, 2021). Information overload is a common feature of a digital media environment, where traditional media must compete with multiple digital information sources. Due to many sources, information consumers experience an overload of information, but they are able to handle the amount of information they are exposed to (Simon & Camargo, 2021).

During chaotic periods, such as COVID-19, where the role of media is important and new media is especially highly esteemed. Also, media can help in reducing uncertainty and enhancing social trust during infodemics. News sites help information consumers to access diverse news by legacy media. News consumption and reliability depend if the news comes from a main-stream news provider or not, this can be difference on social media. Social media can also contribute the enhancement and trust, it acts like an echo chamber where users tend

to share similar opinions on certain topics, despite the news is right or wrong. This is also the problem with social media everyone can share information without any restriction. This has as resulted social media users can help people feel uncertain and trustworthy in the community. Also, the information can lead to rumors what can be based on dis- or misinformation (Lee, Kim, Park, & Cha, 2021).

Fake News on Media Channels

Based on the answers of 80 citizens of the Netherlands, the result has found that newspapers, news sites, and radio stations are found credible with a score of above 3 (see Figure 2). TV stations can be found credible to a certain point. Social media tends to be more unreliable than credible.

Figure 2. Results “How credible are the media?”

Citizens found it likeliest to encounter fake news on social media, with an average score of 4.34 (see Figure 3). The least likely are newspapers. TV stations, radio stations, and news sites can also tend to be more likely to encounter fake news.

Figure 3. Results “How likely is it that you encounter fake news on a media platform?”

Social media is also the most related medium for fake news according to the survey results (see Figure 4). This is followed by TV station, which are also associated with fake news. Newspapers and news sites are less associated with fake news.

Figure 4. Results “How much do you associate a media platform with fake news?”

80% of the respondents said they have encountered fake news. 17% of the respondents don't know if they have encountered fake news, and 3% of the respondents never encountered fake news (see Figure 5).

Figure 5. Results “Have you ever encountered fake news?”

A factor that is related to an infodemic is also the amount of information. The survey shows that there is a small tendency towards the overwhelming effect of the amount of information. Figure 6 shows the distribution of the results of the survey, 1 is not overwhelming and 5 is very overwhelming. The average score is a 3.30.

Figure 6. Results “Are you overwhelmed by the amount of information?”

DISCUSSION

The digital transformation of the media has given citizens participating power in the media. This has led to an overall decline of the quality of the media

and an incline of the amount of information published. This research shows that there are differences between media channels. Newspapers are found most credible, least likely to publish fake news and least associated with fake news. Whereas social media is found to be least credible, most likely to encounter fake news and most associated with fake news. The overwhelming effect that the amount of information has on our society has a tendency towards more overwhelming.

Data shows that the credibility, likeliness to encounter fake news and association of fake news with media channels are correlated. This is in line with H1: The media has an enhanced effect on infodemic. Media do have an enhanced effect on the infodemic. This research supports H2: Digital transformation amplifies the effect of infodemic. Through the digital transformation of the media, specifically the power for citizens to post their own opinion online, the effect of the infodemic is amplified. Data from this research supports H3: Digital transformation has increased the amount of fake news. The increase in fake news is dependent on the digitalization of media channels, specifically social media.

This research has shown what the effect is of the digital transformation of the social media on the infodemic. Known literature has explained what the impact of the digital transformation of the media has had. Known literature has also explained what an infodemic is, however the term infodemic is not widely used because it is mostly related with pandemics, which is wrong. The infodemic illustrates one of the ongoing crises our society faces. Therefore, this research explains what a cause of the infodemic is, which can help to solve it.

This paper could be seen as a recommendation to media companies to make sure that fake news is limited on their platforms. The media is responsible for creating a platform in which users can express their opinion. This has many advantages and can generally be seen as a good platform; however, algorithms can be made which can detect fake news and give it for example a certain label.

The recommendation to governments is to have a good communication policy and don't overwhelm and underwhelm citizens with the amount of information.

CONCLUSION

The research paper provides an exploratory answer to the research question “How did the digital transformation on the media affect the infodemic?” From the conducted research it can be concluded that due to the digital transformation the increase of citizen participation in the media led to the

enlarged amount of information, including mis-, disinformation and fake news. The latter is most plausible to encounter on social media.

The limitation of this research is that it has primarily focused on the relation between the media and fake news. Fake news is the most known sort of disinformation, however the infodemic also includes misinformation which is not fully supported in this research. However, this research can be found valid because the conclusion can be made that the digital transformation of the media has affected the infodemic, which answers the research question of this paper.

Evaluating the external validity of the primary data there are several aspects which are interesting. Because there is no primary school represented within the respondents (see Appendix 2 – graphs), which is 9% of the Dutch population (CBS, sd.), there is an under-coverage error. Due to time and money limitations this is an acceptable trade-off. In the sample, bachelor graduates are overrepresented, however, the respondents are with broader study backgrounds than initially expected from a convenience sample from pre-master students' professional network. Furthermore, for every 100 women, there are 99 men in the Netherlands (CBS, sd.). The respondents of the survey are 48,75% men which is just 1% lower than the percentage distribution of the Netherlands (see Appendix 2 – graphs). The age distribution of respondents is also reasonable. The Dutch population is largest represented by 50–65-year-olds, but 20–30-year-olds are also more strongly represented than other age ranges. Both categories are also represented in this proportion. The youngest respondent is 18, and the oldest is 80. These findings make it not to be entirely generalizable to a broader population.

Further research is suggested in two aspects. First, additional research is recommended, expanding the limited sample size, increasing generalisability, and providing more substantial evidence for the results. Secondly, it would be relevant to further study the digital transformation of the media and its affect on the infodemic with more consideration of misinformation and disinformation. Furthermore, the evanesce of geographical limits caused by digital transformation may make it relevant whether results differ in other countries.

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APPENDIX 1 – SURVEY**Fake news in media**

Hi!

This survey is for a research on the great amount of accessible information. This research is being conducted by four students from Tilburg University. The results of the survey will be used in a research model. The survey is completely anonymised and it takes about 5 minutes to complete.

Thank you in advance for completing the survey!

* Required

Age*

Gender*

Male/Female/Other:

Education level*

Vwo/Havo/Vmbo / MBO / Bachelor / Master / Other:

What media channels you use?*(multiple answers possible)

Newspapers (e.g. AD, Volkskrant, Telegraaf) / News sites (e.g. NOS, NU.nl) / Social media (e.g. Facebook, Instagram, TikTok) / Radio / TV shows / Other:

How credible are newspapers according to you?*

Not credible 1 2 3 4 5 Very credible

How credible are news sites according to you?*

Not credible 1 2 3 4 5 Very credible

How credible are social media according to you?*

Not credible 1 2 3 4 5 Very credible

How credible are radio stations according to you?*

Not credible 1 2 3 4 5 Very credible

How credible are TV shows according to you?*

Not credible 1 2 3 4 5 Very credible

Have you ever encountered fake news?*

Yes / No / Maybe

When did you first encounter fake news?*

1900 – 2000 / 2001 – 2005 / 2006 – 2010 / 2011 – 2015 / 2016 – 2020 / 2021 – Today / I have never encountered fake news

How likely is it that you encounter fake news in newspapers?*

Not likely 1 2 3 4 5 Very likely

How likely is it that you encounter fake news in news sites?*

Not likely 1 2 3 4 5 Very likely

How likely is it that you encounter fake news in social media?*

Not likely 1 2 3 4 5 Very likely

How likely is it that you encounter fake news in radio stations?*

Not likely 1 2 3 4 5 Very likely

How likely is it that you encounter fake news in TV shows?*

Not likely 1 2 3 4 5 Very likely

How much do you associate newspapers with fake news?*

Not associated 1 2 3 4 5 Very associated

How much do you associate news sites with fake news?*

Not associated 1 2 3 4 5 Very associated

How much do you associate social media with fake news?*

Not associated 1 2 3
4 5 Very associated

How much do you associate radio with fake news?*

Not associated 1 2 3 4 5 Very associated

How much do you associate TV shows with fake news?*

Not associated 1 2 3 4 5 Very associated

Are you ever overwhelmed by the amount of information in the media?*

Not overwhelmed 1 2 3 4 5 Very overwhelmed

APPENDIX 2 – SOCIAL MEDIA PLATFORM

Social media networks worldwide as January 2022, ranked by number of monthly active users (Statista, 2022).

* Platforms have not published numbers in the past 12 months

** Daily active users, monthly active user number is likely higher

APPENDIX 3 – GRAPHS

